

THE FORMATION STRUCTURE OF STUDENTS' SKILLS FOR THE
SUBJECT OF MILITARY EDUCATION

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Vasijonov Abduboqi Ikromjon ugli

Student of the Faculty of Military Education of FerSU

Ashuraliyev Mamarajab Nazirjon ugli

Student of the Faculty of Military Education of FerSU

Ahmadjonov Shahzod Xodijon ugli

Student of the Faculty of Military Education of FerSU

Annotation: *This article develops the structure of primary military education skills for schoolchildren, the structure of students' skills formation through pre-service primary education, scientific, systematic and consistent, interaction of teaching materials, compatibility, visual training in the formation of students' skills based on virtual learning technologies, the principles of providing educational problems, independent learning, distribution of educational material, interest, linking theory with practice are widely covered.*

Keywords: *virtual education, student, school, problem, practice, material, visual training, military education, technical means, interactive, skill, knowledge, technology, independent learning, internet, information, theory.*

Introduction. The concept of development of military education in preschool, secondary, vocational and higher education systems of the Republic of Uzbekistan, thencept of the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2035, PD- 5712- April 29, 2019 and PD-5812 of September 6, 2019 "On additional measures to further improve the system of vocational education" and PD-5847 of October 8, 2019 "On approval of the Concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", The concept of industrial development of Uzbekistan until 2025, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan which is dated on February 23, 2018, by number 140, "On the Concept of educating youth in the spirit of military patriotism" was developed on the basis of the tasks set out in the charter.

The concept of the pre-conscription subject is mainly to improve the pre-conscription competencies of 10th and 11th grade high school students using virtual learning technologies.

Today, due to the rapid development of information and communication technologies, one of the most pressing issues today is the widespread introduction of computer technology and its pedagogical teaching aids in the subject of preschool education. From this point of view, the widespread use of innovative technologies, as well as computer and their teaching aids, including virtual learning technologies has become a serious need in improving the teaching methods of sciencedepartments.

Virtual learning is the ability to visually present learning materials with the help of simulation and technical aids, to create a virtual image of complex processes and events, to

conduct experiments in a virtual way, as well as to prepare complex processes in a virtual form. It is a modern learning environment that encourages methodological support for independent work on learning materials and enhances creative thinking.

Literature review. According to the analysis of scientific and methodological sources and the current state of teaching in secondary special education, it is clear that the solution to the pedagogical problem of improving the effectiveness of teaching the subject in schools depends on the implementation of the following main tasks: The use of new modern computer technologies (e-learning resources, virtual learning technologies, interactive teaching aids, e-textbooks, cloud technologies, e-simulators), abandoning traditional methods in teaching the subject; use of virtual learning technologies to demonstrate some complex processes and events; implementation of learning tasks aimed at developing students' motivation in science; creating a virtual world for students to practice independently; formation of a culture of using Internet technologies and networked educational portals, virtual learning platforms. The interactive capabilities of the global network provide the community opportunities for science education. Through online communication, the listener has the opportunity to collaborate on practical learning projects with their peers. Students will also be able to engage in interactive discussions in a variety of geographic areas once they are exempt from compulsory classes. The military education teacher in charge of distance learning through the Internet will have the opportunity to conduct online discussions, arranging a certain amount of time for students to answer questions and explain topics they do not understand.

In this regard, a number of informal learning environments, virtual learning portals and platforms on the interactive capabilities of the global network and the use of distance learning and related virtual learning technologies have been created and widely used in foreign countries. These include the State University of Pennsylvania (worldcampus.psu.edu), the University of California Virtual University (sms.edu), the Open University of Washington (gwu.edu), Western Governors University (umuc.edu), and the Virtual University of Minnesota (isek.org/sv. /index.JSP), the Center for Distance Learning at the University of Florida (FCD.ufl.edu), the British Open University (open.ac.uk), and the Kharkiv Correspondence University in Germany (tu-dresden.de) are examples of informal learning environments.

Also, the principles of scientific, systematic and coherent, interaction of teaching materials, compatibility, visual teaching, providing educational problems, independent learning, distribution of teaching materials, interest, linking theory with practice are given in the formation of students' skills on the basis of virtual learning technologies. Based on these principles, a virtual learning platform chqbt.uz will be created on the Internet to organize the process of teaching and learning Military Education on the basis of virtual learning technologies. Its structural structure is as follows (see Figure 1). The main aspect of this virtual learning platform to distance learning is the development of the didactic basis of virtual learning technologies, which has the following features: the availability of retraining courses that require less cost than the traditional teaching method. There is no limit to the number of participants; the level of knowledge, the opportunity for in-depth study of skills through repeated peer and self-assessment of the user of the training

courses; the student receives education at a convenient time and place without interruption of work; the ability to reach a wide range of users; the ability to receive more information in visual (textual, audio, video, animated, three-dimensional) form than traditional education; the ability to conduct virtual experiments at difficult times and places; the ability to see processes and events that are difficult to see (walking in a line, standing in a line, disassembling and assembling a weapon, the process of using weapons) competencies are improved.

Analysis and results. Differentiation is derived from the Latin word meaning "difference", which means to divide the whole into different parts, forms, stages, stratification.

Formation of differential teaching skills:

- in this case, the teacher works with a group of students formed in the presence of any common qualities that are important for the learning process (same group);
- part of a general didactic system that provides a specialization of the learning process for different groups of different students.

Differentiated education consists of working in different programs, divided into groups according to the individual characteristics, abilities, interests and needs of each student. Therefore, the differentiation of teaching requires to be individualized education. Individual education is one of the forms of teaching that has a pedagogical impact on the student. Understands the teacher's activities with the student outside the classroom.

Individual education is the oldest form of education and was widely used in ancient times and the Middle Ages. In the history of education in Uzbekistan, the form of individual education has been widely used. Its effect, especially in the applied arts, was manifested in the form of teacher-student education in the craft. Famous national masters Toshpolat Arslonkulov, Usta Shirin Murodov, Kadyrjon Khaydarov, Mahmud Usmanov, Hamro Rakhimov were educated in this way. Individual education provides an opportunity to fully take into account the individual characteristics of the child's psycho-natural tendencies to the field of science and profession.

Individualized learning is a model of the organization of the form and process of teaching, which is specific to the programs of all forms of individualized learning. The main advantage of individual education is that it allows students to organize their learning activities, choose the content, tools and methods of education and take into account their individual characteristics and speed to create. There is an opportunity to do this more effectively through virtual learning technologies.

Taking into account individual characteristics in the design of virtual learning technologies helps to select individual information in teaching and to consolidate the units of information in the field, as well as to shape the skills of the student. This is because students' interest in learning varies, which can help them find the optimal norm.

Organizational forms of independent work of students

Students goals will be highlighted independently and the collection of additional information will be more engaging, providing independent thinking in problem-solving, searching for relevant information, and highlighting the results of their work. The

information in the given program should be aimed at the student's independent acceptance and knowledge. Virtual learning technologies can serve to further improve the quality of education if used not only as an additional aid in education but also as a basic learning tool.

Another way to build students' skills in the subject of Military Education is to use this type of independent learning. The use of virtual learning platforms placed on the Internet in the organization of independent learning gives good results. To do this, it is necessary to follow the following didactic tasks: to provide accurate and complete information on the topic under study; increase visual education (creating a virtual view of the sections of the subject of Military Education); increase the volume of independent work of students (increase of scientific knowledge by carrying out the given tasks); deepening the activity of students, ensuring their optimal and rapid growth in military service; maximum satisfaction of students' interest in learning; organization of feedback; monitor students' performance (for example, by conducting an online test to determine their initial level of knowledge and knowledge acquired after studying certain sections of the CBT) and provide them with the necessary guidance; reading additional literature on science and independent use of virtual learning technologies posted on the Internet.

To perform these didactic tasks, it is necessary to develop science-based 3-D format virtual learning technologies.

The tools used are software tools (MS PowerPoint, prezi.com, Turbo Site, I-Spring Suite), technical tools (computer, video gun, smart board).

The creation of virtual learning technologies should be carried out in the following order:

1. Identify topics where virtual learning technologies are created;
2. Selection of modern pedagogical software;
3. Select the appropriate coverage for the purpose and topic of virtual education;
4. Development of a scenario and structure of virtual education;
6. Selection of educational material;
7. Development of the structure of educational materials;
8. Development of a multimedia component;
9. Approbation;
10. Documentation (official registration from the Intellectual Property Agency, assignment of copyright).

Teaching VAT with the help of virtual learning technologies is a new stage in the use of computers for the educational process, and modern educational platforms for traditional and distance learning systems are being created and used. This creates a wide range of opportunities for the organization of effective communication between and students of military education and the independent study of the subject.

Conclusion. The most important task of the head of military education is the formation of students' skills in the subject of Pre-Military Education. This can be done effectively through the Internet. The resources that make up a virtual learning platform for students on the Internet can include graphics, animation, pictures, sound effects, and textual information. In other words, a virtual learning platform incorporates a combination of different means of presenting information integrated into a single content.

The exchange or combination of text, graphics, video and audio presentations allows the formation of motivation, new knowledge and skills by conveying educational information in a form that is as clear and easy to master as possible.

To perform these didactic tasks, it is necessary to create a virtual learning platform on the Internet. It should include methodological - normative (curriculum, program); information-educational (text of lectures in electronic form, notes of electronic short lectures, the electronic text of the textbook, multimedia applications, electronic scientific manual); information - auxiliary (dictionaries, presentations); practice-oriented (tasks for independent work of students, virtual practical work, methodical instructions, etc.); control-diagnostics (tasks for self-control); monitoring function (control work questions and tasks, course work, abstract topics, test questions).

In order to attract students to patriotic and military duties, it is necessary to develop modern virtual learning technologies in the field of CBT. Virtual learning technologies allow students to edit and simplify working papers, independent work provided by military education leaders and teachers.

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